

MANUSCRIPT TEXT RECOGNITION ALGORITHMS RESULTS ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

In the case of handwritten text recognition, the image processing, line, word, and letter segmentation algorithms, their processing structures are given, CNN neural network operation mode description is described. Modern hardware has been described as a more improved view of a high-performance product that achieves high results through neural networks. The results are based on the images of the data set available in the neural networks and the data set formed for the Uzbek language. Through this neural network structure, 93% kb recognition efficiency was achieved.

Keywords initial processing, recognition, segmentation, neural network, CNN

Introduction

In today's era of advanced information technology, large amounts of handwritten data can be fraught with recognition errors Automatic handwriting detection can dramatically reduce the time required to transcribe large amounts of text, and also serves as a basis for developing future applications of Machine Learning. Handwritten character recognition is a field of continuous research that involves the identification of artificial intelligence writing graphics. An algorithm that performs handwriting detection can take and identify features from images, touch screen devices, and convert them into machine-readable form. There are two main types of handwriting detection - online and offline. Both types can be used in applications for step-by-step learning based on user feedback when conducting offline learning on data in parallel. Several approaches have been used to recognize online and offline handwriting, such as statistical methods, systematic methods, neural networks, and syntactic methods. Some recognition systems detect strokes, while others use recognition in a single character or whole words.

Neural network-based handwritten character recognition system with feature separation.

The problem of initial processing and segmentation of the image

Correctly recognizing the characters, the initial processing of the image is very important. These methods typically include noise removal, image segmentation, cropping, scaling, and more. The recognition system first accepts the scanned image as input. Images can be in JPG or UN format. Digital photography and image modification often cause noise, making

it difficult to determine what part of the object of interest is. When we look at the problem of character recognition, we want to minimize noise as much as possible while maintaining the impact of the characters, as they are important for proper classification. The following are important when processing an image:

The analysis consists of two stages. The first stage deals with the brightness and contrast statistics of segmented characters. The characters are then normalized and processed with a fragmentation algorithm. Since fragmentation and brightness normalization violate the statistical properties of segmented characters, the first step of the analysis must be performed before applying the fragmentation algorithm. Also, the height of the defined segments is the same for all characters. In this regard, once you have applied the fragmentation algorithm, you will need to continue to analyze the dimensions. Given the above limitations, the sequence of steps can be structured as follows:

1. Divide the text into segments
2. Analyze the brightness and contrast of the segments and eliminate faults.
3. Use the algorithm for separating letter parts by segments (result in Figure 1).
4. Analyze the dimensions of the segments and eliminate the faults.

Figure-1. Character segments

If we assume that there are no significant differences in the brightness and contrast of the segments, then it is possible to exclude segments that differ significantly from the average value. Let i -segment of the image text be given by a discrete function $f_i(x, y)$, where w_i and h_i are the dimensions of the element. Determine the following statistical properties of the element:

The global brightness of such a segment is defined as the average value of the brightness of individual pixels:

$$p_b^{(i)} = \sum_{x=0}^{w_i} \sum_{y=0}^{h_i} f(x, y)$$

The global contrast of the i -segment is defined as the standard deviation of the individual pixel brightness:

$$p_c^{(i)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{x=0}^{w_i} \sum_{y=0}^{h_i} (p_b^{(i)} - f(x, y))^2}{w_i h_i}}$$

The function $f(x, y)$ only represents the intensity of gray images, but additional color heuristics can be used to improve the recognition process. This analysis distinguishes between characteristic and non-characteristic elements based on color. If the resulting image is

represented by the HSV color model, we can directly calculate the global color and saturation of the segments as the average color and saturation of the individual pixels [1-2]:

$$p_h^{(i)} = \sum_{x=0}^{w_i} \sum_{y=0}^{h_i} h(x, y); \quad p_s^{(i)} = \sum_{x=0}^{w_i} \sum_{y=0}^{h_i} s(x, y)$$

These given here are $h(x, y)$ and $s(x, y)$ the color and saturation of the exact pixel in the HSV color model. If the captured image is in the RGB color model, you must first convert it to the HSV model.

The recognition process can be represented by the following model:

Figure 2: Structured application process model

The purpose of the process model is:

- 1) Image
- 2) Image pre-processing and segmentation.
- 3) Evaluate the perspective of an external observer who reviews how the process has been implemented and identifies improvements that need to be made to make it more effective.
- 4) Instructor
- 5) Determine the desired processes and how they should be performed/performed establishing rules, guidelines, and patterns of behavior, if followed, will result in the desired process efficiency. They can range from strict adherence to flexible guidelines.
- 6) Explanation
- 7) Explain the rationale for the processes.
- 8) Study and evaluate several possible directions of action based on logical arguments.
- 9) Establish a clear link between the processes and the requirements that the model must meet.

10) Predetermines the points at which data can be retrieved for reporting.

Figure 3. Stages of text recognition

Detection of handwritten symbols using a neural network

Handwritten symbols, ie Uzbek alphabets from A to Ng, are taught. This is done by modeling a neural network that needs to be trained in a data set that contains alphabetical images.

This database contains 3,700 alphabetic images, 28×28 in size, all available as a CSV file.

CNN image classifications take an input image, process it, and classify it into specific categories. Computers view the input image as an array of pixels. Based on the image resolution, it sees $H \times W \times D$ (h = Height, w = Width, d = Size). For example, an image of a $6 \times 6 \times 3$ array of an RGB matrix (assuming 3 RGB values) and an image of a $4 \times 4 \times 1$ array of a matrix on a grayscale where the number of color values of 3 and 1 is the image pixel. The following are the common types of layers on CNN:

Convolution - CNN's main building block is the convolution layer, which is a mathematical operation to combine two sets of data. To create a property map, the convolution is applied to the data entered using the convolution filter. The first layer to distinguish features from the input image is convolution [3-4].

Striding - Introduction image on the number of shifts step called _ Example - If Step 1, we convert the filters to 1 pixel at a time.

Non-linearity - A commonly used activation function means Rectified Linear Unit for non-linear operation of RELU. Output:

$$\{F(x) = \max(0, x)\}$$

Pooling Layer - After the convolution operation is usually combined to reduce the size. This allows you to reduce the number of parameters, which in turn reduces training time and reduces the likelihood of over-adaptation. Combining layers takes a pattern independently of each feature map, reducing height and width and maintaining depth. Unlike convolution operation, merging has no parameters. It slides the window over its input and simply takes the maximum value in the window. The largest element from the properties map is selected using this operation [5-].

Figure 4: Convolutional neural network architecture

The main reason for the success of the structure of a convolutional neural network was the concept of common weights. Despite their large size, these networks have few configurable parameters compared to their ancestor, the neocognitron. There are variants of the structure of a convolutional neural network (tilde convolutional neural network), similar to the neocognitron, in such networks there is a partial rejection of the associated weights, but the learning algorithm remains the same and is based on the back propagation of the error. Structure of a convolutional neural network can quickly run on a serial machine and quickly learn by pure parallelization of the convolution process on each map, as well as inverse convolution when propagating an error through the network.

Figure 5: Neural network model

Input layer: The input data is a color image of the JPEG type, 28x28 pixels in size. If the size is too large, then the computational complexity will increase, respectively, the restrictions on the speed of the answer will be violated, the determination of the size in this problem is solved by the selection method. If you choose a size too small, the network will not be able to detect key facial features. Each image is divided into 3 channels: red, blue, green. Thus, 3 images of 28x28 pixels are obtained. The input layer takes into account the two-dimensional topology of images and consists of several maps (matrices), there can be one map if the image is presented in grayscale, otherwise there are 3 of them, where each map corresponds to an image with a specific channel (red, blue and green).

The input data for each specific pixel value is normalized to a range of 0 to 1, using the formula:

$$f(p, \min, \max) = \frac{P - \min}{\max - \min}$$

f- Normalization functions,

p- Colors (0..255)

min- colors min value (0)

max- colors max value(255)

Convolutional layer

The convolutional layer is a set of maps (another name is feature maps, in everyday life these are ordinary matrices), each map has a synaptic core (it is called differently in different sources: a scanning core or a filter).

The number of cards is determined by the requirements for the task, if you take a large number of cards, then the quality of recognition will increase, but the computational complexity will increase. Based on the analysis of scientific articles, in most cases it is proposed to take a ratio of one to two, that is, each map of the previous layer (for example, the first convolutional layer, the previous one is the input) is associated with two maps of the convolutional layer.

Figurer 6: Organization of links between maps of the convolutional layer and the previous one

The sizes of all maps of the convolutional layer are the same and are calculated by the formula:

$$(w, h) = (mw - kw + 1, mH - kH + 1)$$

The kernel is a filter or window that slides over the entire area of the previous map and finds certain features of objects. For example, if the network was trained on many faces, then one of the cores could produce the greatest signal in the region of the eye, mouth, eyebrow, or nose during the training process, while the other core could detect other features. The size of the kernel is usually taken in the range from 3x3 to 7x7. If the size of the nucleus is small, then it will not be able to highlight any signs, if it is too large, then the number of connections between neurons increases. Also, the size of the kernel is chosen so that the size of the maps of the convolutional layer is even, this allows you not to lose information when reducing the dimension in the subsample layer, described below.

The core is a system of shared weights or synapses, this is one of the main features of a convolutional neural network. In a conventional multilayer network, there are a lot of connections between neurons, that is, synapses, which greatly slows down the detection process. In a convolutional network, on the contrary, common weights reduce the number of connections and allow you to find the same feature throughout the entire image area.

Initially, the values of each map of the convolutional layer are equal to 0. The values of the kernel weights are set randomly in the range from -0.5 to 0.5. The kernel slides over the previous map and performs a convolution operation that is often used for image processing, the formula is:

$$(f * g)[m, n] = \sum f[m - k - l] * g[k, l]$$

f- Input image matrix

g- Convolution kernel

The convolution operation and getting the values of the convolution map. The core is shifted, the new map is the same size as the previous one (same)

In this case, depending on the method of processing the edges of the original matrix, the result may be smaller than the original image (valid), the same size (same) or larger (full).

In a simplified form, this layer can be described by the formula:

$$x^l = f(x^{l-1} * k^l + b^l)$$

x^l Output layer l ;

$f()$ – Activation function;;

b^l Displacement coefficient of the layer;

* Wrapper implementation of x input with k cores..

In this case, due to edge effects, the size of the initial matrices decreases, the formula:

$$x_j^l = f(\sum x_i^{l-1} * k_j^l + b_j^l),$$

This x_j^l character card (l layer output);

$f()$ – Activation function;;

b^l Shift coefficient of layer l for character card;

k_j^l k - j card, l layer Wrapped core;

*- Wrapper implementation of x input with k cores..

Subsample layer

The subsample layer, like the convolutional layer, has maps, but their number coincides with the previous layer, there are 6 of them. The purpose of the layer is to reduce the dimension of the maps of the previous layer. If some features have already been identified during the previous convolution operation, then such a detailed image is no longer needed for further processing, and it is compressed to a less detailed one. In addition, filtering out unnecessary details helps not to retrain.

Formally, the layer can be described by the formula:

$$x^l = f(a^l * \text{subsample}(x^{l-1}) + b^l)$$

x^l - Layer output l;

$f()$ – Activation function;

a^l, b^l Layer displacement coefficients;

Subsample () - is an operation for sampling local maximum values.

Fully Connected Layer: The last of the layer types is the conventional multilayer perceptron layer. The purpose of the layer - classification, models a complex non-linear function, optimizing which improves the quality of recognition.

The neurons of each map of the previous subsample layer are connected to one neuron of the hidden layer. Thus, the number of neurons in the hidden layer is equal to the number of maps of the subsample layer, but the connections may not necessarily be the same, for example, only part of the neurons of any of the maps of the subsample layer can be connected to the first neuron of the hidden layer, and the rest to the second, or all neurons of the first maps are

connected with neurons 1 and 2 of the hidden layer. The calculation of neuron values can be described by the formula:

$$x_j^l = f\left(\sum x_j^{l-1} * w_{i,j}^{l-1} + b_j^{l-1}\right),$$

x_j^l Character card (l layer output);

$f()$ -- activation function;

b^l Layer displacement coefficients;

$w_{i,j}^l$ Matrix of weight coefficients of the layer.

Output layer

The output layer is connected to all neuron and predydushchego layer. Kolichestvo neuronov sootvetstvuet kolichestvu raspoznavayemykh klassov, to est 2 – simbol i ne simbol. For the reduction of the number of connections and the calculation for the binary case, it is possible to use the hyperbolic tangent when using the hyperbolic tangent function, the output of the neuron with the value of -1 indicates the affinity for the class "no symbol", on the contrary, the output of the neuron with the value of 1 - indicates the affinity for the class symbol

The coding part of the project was done in google collaboration. Because google collaboration uses very much easy. Google on the server technician servers that are too large on the side make our job easier.

The required libraries are loaded before the project.

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import cv2
import numpy as np
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Dense, Flatten, Conv2D, MaxPool2D, Dropout
# from keras.optimizers import SGD, Adam
from keras.callbacks import ReduceLROnPlateau, EarlyStopping
# from keras.utils import to_categorical
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.utils import shuffle
```

Now we will teach the data set and print the first 10 images using data. Head (10).

```
data = pd.read_csv("/content/drive/MyDrive/Magistrlik_desertatsiya/archive/Handwritten_Data.csv").astype('float32')
print(data.head(10))
```

```
[*]
   0  0.1  0.2  0.3  0.4  0.5  ...  0.643  0.644  0.645  0.646  0.647  0.648
0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
1  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
2  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
3  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
4  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
5  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
6  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
7  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
8  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0
9  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  ...  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0

[10 rows x 785 columns]
```

(The image above shows some rows of data frame data using the data frame's head () function)

We divide the information into pictures and their labels:

```
X = data.drop('0',axis = 1)
y = data['0']
```

Read information into pictures and their corresponding labels, "0" contains the labels, so we download the "0" column from the readable data frame and use it in y to form the labels.

Reshape data in a CSV file to display as an image:

```
train_x, test_x, train_y, test_y = train_test_split(X, y, test_size = 0.2)

train_x = np.reshape(train_x.values, (train_x.shape[0], 28,28))
test_x = np.reshape(test_x.values, (test_x.shape[0], 28,28))

print("Train data shape: ", train_x.shape)
print("Test data shape: ", test_x.shape)
```

Train data shape: (297960, 28, 28)
Test data shape: (74490, 28, 28)

Data into a training and test data set using train test_ split ().

In addition, the train and test image data are reshaped to display as an image, as originally in the CSV file they contained 784 of the pixel data [7-8].

All labels are available in the form of floating-point values, we convert them to integer values and so we create a word dictionary to compare integer values with characters.

Draw the number of alphabets in the data set:

```
y_int = np.int0(y)
count = np.zeros(26, dtype='int')
for i in y_int:
    count[i] +=1

alphabets = []
for i in word_dict.values():
    alphabets.append(i)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1,1, figsize=(10,10))
ax.barh(alphabets, count)

plt.xlabel("Number of elements ")
plt.ylabel("Alphabets")
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```

First, the labels are converted to integer values and added to the list of calculations by the label. This calculation list contains the number of images in the data set for each alphabet.

A list containing all the characters is now created using the dictionary's values () function.

Now calculate and use the following list of alphabets

Data mixing:

```

▶ shuff = shuffle(train_x[:100])

fig, ax = plt.subplots(3,3, figsize = (10,10))
axes = ax.flatten()

for i in range(9):
    _, shu = cv2.threshold(shuff[i], 30, 200, cv2.THRESH_BINARY)
    axes[i].imshow(np.reshape(shuff[i], (28,28)), cmap="Greys")
plt.show()

```

Now we mix up some pictures of the train set.

Mixing is done using the shuffle () function so that we can display some random images.

Then we create 9 pictures in 3 × 3 formats and display the limited images of 9 alphabets.

(The picture above shows the images in grayscale we took from the data set)

Data reshaping:

Train and reshape the test data set for inclusion in the model.

```

▶ train_X = train_x.reshape(train_x.shape[0],train_x.shape[1],train_x.shape[2],1)
print("New shape of train data: ", train_X.shape)

test_X = test_x.reshape(test_x.shape[0], test_x.shape[1], test_x.shape[2],1)
print("New shape of train data: ", test_X.shape)

↳ New shape of train data: (297960, 28, 28, 1)
New shape of train data: (74490, 28, 28, 1)

```

Here we convert single float values to categorical values. This is done by the CNN model inserting tags and producing the output as a probability vector.

```

train_yOHE = to_categorical(train_y, num_classes = 26, dtype='int')
print("New shape of train labels: ", train_yOHE.shape)

test_yOHE = to_categorical(test_y, num_classes = 26, dtype='int')
print("New shape of test labels: ", test_yOHE.shape)

```

```

New shape of train labels: (297960, 26)
New shape of test labels: (74490, 26)

```

Example of CNN logic odor view:

After the convolution layers, the max pool layers, which are typically used to reduce the number of properties obtained, and finally the output of the max pool and layers and the convolution layers are aligned to a one-dimensional vector and given as input to the dense layer (Full connected network).

The created model is as follows:

```

model = Sequential()

model.add(Conv2D(filters=32, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(28,28,1)))
model.add(MaxPool2D(pool_size=(2, 2), strides=2))

model.add(Conv2D(filters=64, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu', padding = 'same'))
model.add(MaxPool2D(pool_size=(2, 2), strides=2))

model.add(Conv2D(filters=128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu', padding = 'valid'))
model.add(MaxPool2D(pool_size=(2, 2), strides=2))

model.add(Flatten())

model.add(Dense(64,activation = "relu"))
model.add(Dense(128,activation = "relu"))

model.add(Dense(26,activation = "softmax"))

```

Above is the CNN model, which is designed to teach this model in a training data set.

Compile and install the model

```

model.compile(optimizer = Adam(learning_rate=0.001), loss='categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])
history = model.fit(train_X, train_yOHE, epochs=1, validation_data = (test_X,test_yOHE))

```

```

9312/9312 [=====] - 456s 49ms/step - loss: 0.1546 - accuracy: 0.9579 - val_loss: 0.0785 - val_accuracy: 0.9781

```

Here we construct a model in which we define the optimization function and the loss function used for adaptation.

The optimization function in use is Adam, i.e. a combination of RMS prop and ADAGRAM optimization algorithms.

The data set is very large, so we only train for one period, but when needed, we can also train it for several periods (recommended to identify the characters to be more precise) is provided).

```

model.summary()
model.save(r'model_hand.h5')

```

Now we get a model summary showing what the different layers defined in the model are and save the model using the model save () function.

```
Model: "sequential_1"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
-----
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)           (None, 26, 26, 32)         320
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling  (None, 13, 13, 32)         0
2D)
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)           (None, 13, 13, 64)         18496
max_pooling2d_4 (MaxPooling  (None, 6, 6, 64)           0
2D)
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)           (None, 4, 4, 128)          73856
max_pooling2d_5 (MaxPooling  (None, 2, 2, 128)          0
2D)
flatten_1 (Flatten)         (None, 512)                 0
dense_3 (Dense)             (None, 64)                  32832
dense_4 (Dense)             (None, 128)                 8320
dense_5 (Dense)             (None, 26)                  3354
-----
Total params: 137,178
Trainable params: 137,178
Non-trainable params: 0
-----
```

(Summary of the identified model)

Getting Train and Validation Accuracies & Losses (Getting the Train & Validation Accuracies & Losses)

```
print("The validation accuracy is :", history.history['val_accuracy'])
print("The training accuracy is :", history.history['accuracy'])
print("The validation loss is :", history.history['val_loss'])
print("The training loss is :", history.history['loss'])
```

```
The validation accuracy is : [0.9781044721603394]
The training accuracy is : [0.9578869938850403]
The validation loss is : [0.07850617170333862]
The training loss is : [0.15458224713802330]
```

In the code segment above, we publish training and validation accuracy, as well as training and verification losses to identify characters.

Make some predictions based on test data:

```
fig, axes = plt.subplots(3,3, figsize=(8,9))
axes = axes.flatten()

for i,ax in enumerate(axes):
    img = np.reshape(test_X[i], (28,28))
    ax.imshow(img, cmap="Greys")

    pred = word_dict[np.argmax(test_yOHE[i])]
    ax.set_title("Prediction: "+pred)
    ax.grid()
```

Here we are creating 9 thumbnails in Figure (3, 3) and visualizing the alphabets of some sets of test data created using the model predict () function to determine the text, along with their predictions.

Prediction in the external image

```
img = cv2.imread('/content/drive/MyDrive/Magistrlik desertatsiya/archive/img_B.png')
img_copy = img.copy()
img = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
img = cv2.resize(img, (400,440))
```

Here we first read the external image, which is an image of the alphabet “B”, and created a copy of it, i.e. we have to go through some processing to access the model for the prediction we can see after a while.

The image reading is then converted from the BGR view (Open CV reads the image in BGR format) to RGB to display the image and resized to the desired size where we want to display the image.

```
img_copy = cv2.GaussianBlur(img_copy, (7,7), 0)
img_gray = cv2.cvtColor(img_copy, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
_, img_thresh = cv2.threshold(img_gray, 100, 255, cv2.THRESH_BINARY_INV)

img_final = cv2.resize(img_thresh, (28,28))
img_final = np.reshape(img_final, (1,28,28,1))
```

Now we will process the copied image (image copy).

We convert the image from BGR to gray and apply a border to it. We don’t have to use a boundary where we can use grayscale to make predictions, but we do it to keep the image smooth without any fuzzy grays that can lead to incorrect predictions in the image.

Then use the cv2.resize () function to change the image size to what you accept as model input, and use np.reshape () to change the image to use as model input.

```
img_pred = word_dict[np.argmax(model.predict(img_final))]
from google.colab.patches import cv2_imshow

cv2.putText(img, "Prediction: " + img_pred, (20,410), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_DUPLEX, 1.3, color = (255,0,30))
cv2_imshow( img)
```

Now we make a prediction using the processed image and use NP ARGMAX function to get the class index with the highest estimated probability. With this, we get to know the exact character through the word dictionary. Then this predicted character is shown in the picture.

The result of the accuracy graph obtained when the letters are trained is as follows:

This program results:

Table 1. Table of handwriting recognition results

No	manuscripts names	Obtained results
1	Turkiy Guliston	90.86
2	Guliston	89.82
4	Days gone by	90.18

Conclusions

Character recognition (Text Recognition) has been successfully developed using the Python, Tensor flow, and Machine Learning libraries. The handwritten characters achieved recognition results with more than 93% test accuracy. Historical manuscript sources in the library, mail manuscript sources, help to automatically transfer the completed questionnaires in the banking system to the computer in electronic form. Preliminary processing of images leads to an increase in recognition of correct segmentation, the formation of a sufficient data set. This has resulted in work efficiency of more than 90 percent in the work process.

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